

F·A·A·M facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B301
Date: 27 June 2007
Take Off: 09:51:19
Landing: 14:31:00
Flight Time: 4h 39m 41s

Campaign: GERBIL

Operating Area: Niamey -> Nouakchott

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	core chem.	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Mission scientist 1	Jim Haywood	Met Office
7	Mission scientist 2	Ben Johnson	Met Office
8	AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	Filters	Paula Formenti	University of Paris 12 (LISA)
10	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
11	CCM2	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
12	Neph/PSAP/SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
13	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
14	Mission Scientist 3	John Marsham	Leeds University

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B301
 Date: 27 June 2007
 Project: GERBIL
 Location: Niamey -> Nouakchott

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
093236		gin	0.80 kft	097	on
093248		inu	0.81 kft	097	to navigate
093302		cgps	0.80 kft	097	B301cgps.log
093319		wow	0.80 kft	097	set
094608		ASP	0.80 kft	086	open
095119		T/O	0.78 kft	267	Niamey
095200	101434	Profile 1	1.3 - 22.0 kft	269	start at T/O
095217		psap	1.5 kft	270	flow on at T/O
095237		heimann	1.8 kft	270	open at 100ft
095543		video	4.4 kft	313	#1 ffc, #2 dfc; start
101435	105350	Run 1.1	22.0 kft	309	
101441		sonde1	22.0 kft	310	
101927		bbr	22.0 kft	310	retract
102134		heimann	22.0 kft	311	cal 11
103358		Video	22.0 kft	309	#1 ffc, #2 dfc(change)
103956		Sonde 2	22.0 kft	313	
105350	111343	Profile 2	22.0 - 2.2 kft	313	
105423		bbr	21.6 kft	314	extend
105434		heimann	21.4 kft	314	cal 11
111343	111717	Run 2.1	2.2 kft	306	
111445		!	2.2 kft	305	2300ft on qnh1018
111607		bbr	2.2 kft	306	retract
111807		Profile 3	2.2 - 2.4 kft	273	
111807	133221	Run 3.1	2.9 kft	265	
112803		Video	2.9 kft	271	#1, #2 end
112827		Video	2.9 kft	270	#3 ffc & #4dfc start
114130		psap	2.9 kft	271	filter change 1>2
120821		psap	2.9 kft	269	filter change 2>3
130145		Video	2.9 kft	272	#3 #4 end
130211		Video	2.9 kft	272	#5 ffc, #6 dfc; start
133221	135031	Profile 4	2.9 - 20.0 kft	267	
133409		bbr	4.6 kft	268	extend
133424		heimann	4.8 kft	268	cal 14
134008		gin	10.4 kft	269	recycled
135031	140456	Run 4.1	20.0 kft	267	
135046		Sonde3	20.0 kft	268	
140456	143100	Profile 5	20.0 - 0.08 kft		
135103		bbr	20.0 kft	268	retract
142503		P5	2.1 kft	283	interrupt
142717		P5	2.1 kft	207	resumed
143100		Land	0.08 kft	218	nouakchott

B301 Track 27-JUN-07

FAAM sortie brief

GERBILS

Flight No: B301

27th June 2007Objectives

1. Validation of CAMM dust forecast.
2. Measure radiative effect of Saharan dust over the dessert.
3. Insitu sampling of Saharan dust.
4. Measure the surface albedo and surface longwave emission of the Sahara dessert along 18N.

Location

From Niamey to Nouakchott over dessert areas along 18N.

Expected weather

Cloudy and relatively clean atmosphere near Niamey. Moderate dust loadings along 18N. Thin cirrus likely all the way along 18N.

Special requirements

Dropsondes.

Instruments of importance

Nephelometers (wet and dry)

PCASP

PSAP

BBRs

SWS

ARIES

Flight pattern

1. Take off from Niamey at 10Z (11L).
2. Profile climb to above dust layer at 1000ft/min, then accelerate climb to FL240 once above dust [25mins].
3. SLR at FL240 altitude towards 18N 3.6W (FIR boundary) [40mins, T=65mins].
4. Drop a sonde 20mins after start of high-level SLR.
5. Profile down to low-level (suggest 3,000ft) at 1000ft/min in dust layer aiming to be at low-levels on reaching FIR boundary [20mins, T=85mins].
6. SLR along 18N at low-level (suggest 3,000ft) until approximately 10W (KONAD) [120mins, T=205mins].
7. Profile ascent to a level above dust (suggest FL200) at 1000ft/min, followed by SLR at that level [45mins, T=250mins].
8. Profile descent into Nouakchott at 1000ft/min [20mins, T=270mins].
9. Land Nouakchot. Total time = 4:30.

Mission scientist debrief

B301 – GERBILS flight Niamey to Nouakchott

Location

From Niamey to 18N 3.6W and along 18N from 3.6W to 16W (Nouakchott).

Mission aims

Radiative effect of Saharan dust over North Africa. Insitu sampling of Saharan dust aerosol. Surface characterization. CAMM dust forecast validation.

Weather

Extensive mid and high level cloud around Niamey. Clearing up on reaching 18N but still some cirrus at some points along 18N later in flight.

Flight plans

No pirouettes. Take off 10Z from Niamey. Profile ascent to FL220 showed very little aerosol in BL but reasonable dust above 5000ft (neph 50-100). SLR for 40mins at FL220 won't be much use due to cloud both above and below. Profile to 2,300ft (MPA) finishing at 18N 3.6W. Quick run at 2,300ft then ascent to 3000ft due to terrain and poor visibility. A 2:15 run at 3000ft along 18N. Dust concentration was moderate or high all the way. Variations in dust colour, angstrom exponent, size distribution and neph scattering noted along the way. The thickest bit of dust was in a very shallow layer below 5000ft, thought to be produced by a cold pool / gust front outflow from large meso-scale convective systems to the south. Dust generally decreased along run and became finer particles with less negative angstrom exponent. Low-level run finished at 11.6W with a profile ascent to FL200, a short run at that level and a profile descent into Nouakchott. Coincidence with MISR overpass was achieved at 18N 3.6-5.5W about 30-60mins after the overpass time. Sky was observed to be clear (can't rule out very thin cirrus) for this bit of work and SWS did scanning runs and a series of up and down viewing. Later on cirrus was observed so SWS looked down to characterise surface. During last 10mins of low-level leg SWS looked up and down as cirrus had cleared. Three sondes dropped. Two on the high-level SLR between Niamey and 18N line, and one at the beginning of the final SLR at 18N 13W.

Summary

Excellent flight for insitu characterization and validation of CAMM dust concentration. Also should provide another MISR comparison case. Surface characterizations should be possible along much of the low-level run although there was significant dust below that might be a problem in the thickest bits of dust.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.301** Date **27/6/07** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **1** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
095119	T10			NIAMEY	⁶¹⁸ mid and upper cloud from
095119	P1				convective systems of
101435	↑ P1.1				previous evening / night
101435	End	FL220			
101509	Drop1				
1030		FL220	310	15.3N ^{0.3} W	patchy but quite thick and extensive cloud above and below
103956	Drop2	FL220	315	16.N 1.1W	
1040					Dust thickening below cirrus thinning out above generally cirrus in thick discrete small patches.
105350	P2	FL220	315	16.9N 2.3W	
1100		FL170	"	17N 2.5W	Dust top at FL170
1103					cirrus look like its gone
11343	End				
11343	R2.1	2,300ft			~ 1250 1250 AGL

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B301** Date **27/6/07** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **2** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
111756	P3	2,300ft -3000ft	270	18N 3-6W FIR boundary	Run at 2,300ft in very thick dust near surface neph ~ 500
111807	R3.1	3000ft		18N 3-7W	Since we think no cirrus above doing a scan look up look down pattern scanning run with sws neph falling to 300
11174					Satellite suggests this is a cold pool / dust front induced dust from last night's MCS
11174					
					Variations of sand ^{dark grey} colour red sand white pockets and dunes.
					Bz rolls - wind variations periodically
1145					Neph upto 400
1145					PSAP ~ $33 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^{-1}$
					$\omega_{\text{dust}} = 0.9 - 0.95$

KONAQ:ETA
1330
start of
ascent

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....**301** Date**27/6/07** Name**Ben Johnson** Page**3** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1159				18N 6W	Beneath a finger of cirrus according to MSG satellite
1205		300ft	270	6-3W 18N	Neph falling to 250 visibility improving humidity dropping, had wind easing, gradually along run wind is from west
		Albedo ~ 0.45			
1218		cirrus overhead, slightly to the left (south) SWS & AIRES pointing down because of cirrus.			
1215		Dust above is looking less thick now dust filter from past hour ^{hour} minutes looks red. (2 taken each 30 mins)			
1225		Neph dropping to 130 Should get good surface characterisation here (7.5W) ~ 1900 ft agl			
1230				18N 8W	surface albedo dropping to 0.2 over dark rocky valley.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.301** Date 27/6/07 Name Ben Johnson Page 4 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1255	R3-1	3000 2700	270	18N 9.3W	Cirrus still above so
	End continued				SWS & AIRES looking down Surface is quite visible even though rad alt is 2200ft so surface Characterization should be ok
1230-1300					neph ~ 120 Variations in color of dust white/yellow/red with neph showing variable red scattering 1130-1200 much more red scattering 1200-1300 more equal scattering
					PCASP fairly regular along run despite large variation in neph scattering. PCASP shows bigger particles earlier on (before 6W). This was confirmed by pink areas on MSG image.
1305				18N low	Slight increase in neph and water vapour (influence of cold pool/ dust front/outflow?) LOCAR model predicted this well.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B301** Date **27/6/07** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **5** of **S**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
133221	P4	3000	270	11.6W 18N	MASSIVE
133221	(End of R3.1)				Seems to be free of cirrus above so last 10 mins had SWS & ARES pointing $\uparrow \downarrow \uparrow \downarrow$
135031	End P4	FL200	270	18N 13W	Dust top at FL170
135046	Sonde3	"	"	"	Few patches of cirrus ahead, no so much behind (hopefully SWS maneuvers were in clear sky)
					less dust on this profile than on P2 coming down into the dust at 3.6W
					Caused ~ 0.8 on P3 (0.2 in the ^{Surface} near layer)
					~ 0.35 on P4
135031	Rk.1	FL200			
140352	PS	FL200			
		-SFC			

1430 ish LAND

Mission Scientist's Log

Supplemental Log

Flight No **B.301**..... Date **27/06/07** Name **Jim Haywood** Page **1** of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
09:41					Lots of alto-stratus - no point in doing pirouettes. T=31C, Td=21C. WS = 17 knots / 88 degs.
09:52:00	P1				Interesting vertical profile with low level monsoon air influencing the surface. Different to previous profiles. Top at FL200
10:14:35	EMPI SFR1	FL220			
10:14:41		FL220		14°5N	Launch sonde #1.
10:39:56		FL220		16N	Launch sonde #2.
					Still Ei above.
10:53:50	EMPI SFR2	FL220 ↓		16°54'N	Still no cloud below.
11:00					Ci almost gone - not affecting upper BBRs now.

Mission Scientist's Log

Supplemental Log

Flight No **B...301**..... Date **27/06/07**..... Name **Jim Haywood**..... Page **2** of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:06					In P2 cant see ground from 10,000ft or 7000ft. Visible from ~6,000ft.
11:14:33	End P2 SF R2-1	FL23	306		
11:16:50					Passing FIR
11:17:17	End R2 SF P3	FL23			
11:17:35	End P3 SF R3-1	FL30	~2000ft AGL		<p>SWS + ARIES moving to scanning U, C, D, ^{up cal down}</p> <p>R31 Appears to be free from Ci above + no cloud above or below. Dusty with neph reaching $500 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ but dropping to $300 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ at 11:35. Back to $400 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ at 11:45.</p>
11:45					
11:55					Still no Ci above.
12:03					———— " ————
12:17					Ci above reported → SWS & ARIES to look down

Mission Scientist's Log

Supplemental Log

Flight No **B.301**..... Date **27/06/07**..... Name **Jim Haywood**..... Page **3** of of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:37					Have passed a dark rock formation at 12:33.
12:41					Still Ci above.
12:55					The vis observations show that white transported dust is in the lee of the yellow dunes.
13:15					A lot of HF interference with lower pyrometer between 13:15 → 13:25.
13:32:21	End P3 St P4	FL30 ↑			Some Ci around still.
13:50:31	End P4 St P4				Launch Sende #3
14:04:55					
14:03:52	End P4.1				
14:04:56	St P5				

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 301

Date: 27/6/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
09:51:00																Start P1 from Takeoff	
09:53:59	80	0.08	1	5	1											FL030	
09:55:21	150	0.09		10	1											FL040	
09:56:26	150	0.11		40	5											FL050	
09:57:35	120	0.11		60	3											FL060	
09:58:36	105	0.11		60	4											FL070	
09:59:48	130	0.12		70	6											FL080	
10:00:54	130	0.12	2	70	10											FL090	
10:01:57	130	0.12		60	7											FL100	
10:02:55	100	0.12	3	50	3											FL110	
10:03:58	95	0.13		50	3											FL120 PCASP Heater on	
10:05:01	95	0.12		50	2											FL130	
10:05:59	85	0.13	4	50	3											FL140	
10:07:02	75	0.10		15	3											FL150	
10:08:02	35	0.15		10	2											FL160	
10:09:02	15	0.15		7	2											FL170	
10:10:11	10	0.20		5	1											FL180	
10:11:20	3	0.12	5	2	1											FL190	
10:12:20	1	0.04		1												FL200	
10:13:30	1	0.05		1												FL210	
10:14:30																End of P1 & Start Run 1.1 @ FL220	
10:15:00	1	0.08	6	1													
10:20:00	1	0.06															
10:25:00	3	0.05		1													
10:30:00	1	0.05		2													
10:35:00	1	0.06		1													
10:40:00	1	0.05															
10:45:00	1	0.05															
10:50:00	1	0.09															
10:53:47																End of Run 1.1 & Start P2 from FL220	
10:54:55	3	0.09		1												FL210	
10:55:56	2	0.08	7													FL200	
10:56:54	1	0.06		1												FL190	
10:57:52	2	0.08		1												FL180	
10:58:51	10	0.12		20	3											FL170	
10:59:46	70	0.13		60	3											FL160	
11:00:43	85	0.14		90	8											FL150	
11:01:57	100	0.13		80	9											FL140	
11:02:47	90	0.14	8	80	8											FL130	
11:03:48	105	0.13		80	10											FL120	
11:04:46	110	0.13	9	90	8											FL110	
11:05:43	140	0.13		90	8											FL100	
11:06:48	155	0.12	10	100	8											FL090 PCASP heater off	
11:07:51	170	0.12		100	8											FL080	
11:08:55	180	0.12	11	100	10											FL070	
11:10:01	175	0.12	12	100	10											FL060	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 301

Date: 27/6/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:10:56	180	0.14	14	100	10											FL050	
11:11:50	355	0.17	15	300	40	5	200									FL040	
11:12:55	400	0.16	17	300	30	6	200									FL030	
11:13:50																End of P2 & Start Run 2.1 @ FL022	
11:14:00	380	0.16	20	300	40	3	200										
11:16:00	400	0.16	29	300	20	3	100										
11:17:12																End of Run 2.1 & Start P3	
11:18:04																End of P3 & Start Run 3.1 @ FL030	
11:19:00	350	0.16	41	300	30	4	150										
11:21:00	340	0.15	42	200	30	4	150										
11:23:00	300	0.15		200	20	4	150										
11:25:00	380	0.15		200	20	5	150										
11:27:00	300	0.14		200	10	7	150										
11:29:00	350	0.14		200	10	2	100										
11:31:00	340	0.13		150	10	5	100										
11:33:00	360	0.14		150	10	4	150									Note the drop off in detected particles in FFSSP	
11:35:00	310	0.13		150	10	4	200										
11:37:00	310	0.13		125	10	7	200										
11:39:00	320	0.14		150	10	4	600										
11:41:00	340	0.14		150	15	7	150										
11:43:00	300	0.14		150	15	4	100										
11:45:00	310	0.14		150	15	4	100										
11:47:00	330	0.15		200	10	1	100										
11:49:00	360	0.15		300	10	4	200										
11:51:00	360	0.15		300	10	3	300										
11:53:00	350	0.15		300	10	3	300										
11:55:00	340	0.15	43	300	20	1	150										
11:57:00	340	0.15		300	10	2											
11:59:00	335	0.14	48	200	10	1	150										
12:01:00	310	0.13	52	150	10	1	200										
12:03:00	300	0.12	54	100	3	4	75										
12:05:00	290	0.12	57	100	8	1	100										
12:07:00	260	0.12	59	100	8	2	50										
12:09:00	280	0.12	60	100	10	1	200										
12:11:00	280	0.11	63	100	8	1	300										
12:13:00	300	0.11	65	100	8												
12:15:00	320	0.11	66	100	10	4	300										
12:17:00	280	0.12	68	100	9												
12:19:00	280	0.11	69	90	9	1	150										
12:21:00	300	0.10	70	90	8												
12:23:00	300	0.10	74	80	8												
12:25:00	300	0.10	78	80	8												
12:27:00	270	0.09	81	80	8												
12:29:00	280	0.09	85	70	5	1	100										
12:31:00	290	0.09	88	70	5	1	100										
12:33:00	300	0.10	91	100	5	1	100										

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 301

Date: 27/6/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:35:00	300	0.09	94	80	8												
12:37:00	300	0.10	99	80	3												
12:39:00	290	0.10	101	80	3												
12:41:00	300	0.10	104	70	3												
12:43:00	250	0.10	106	70	4												
12:45:00	260	0.10	109	70	4												
12:47:00	260	0.10	113	70	4												
12:49:00	290	0.10	116	70	4												
12:51:00	270	0.10	119	70	3												
12:53:00	270	0.09	121	60	3												
12:55:00	290	0.09	125	70	4												
12:57:00	290	0.09	128	70	3												
12:59:00	270	0.10	130	60	3												
13:01:00	280	0.09	133	70	3												
13:03:00	290	0.10	136	80	3												
13:05:00	280	0.11	141	90	3												
13:07:00	270	0.11	142	90	6												
13:09:00	300	0.10	143	80	5												
13:11:00	300	0.10		80	3												
13:13:00	320	0.09	144	70	6												
13:15:00	325	0.09		70	3												
13:17:00	300	0.09	145	60	5												
13:19:00	305	0.09		60	3												
13:21:00	300	0.09	146	50	3												
13:23:00	305	0.09		50	3												
13:25:00	290	0.09	147	50	3												
13:27:00	240	0.09		50	2												
13:29:00	230	0.09	148	60	3												
13:31:00	250	0.09		50	3												
13:32:17																End of Run 3.1 & Start P4	
13:33:30	200	0.09	149	50	3											FL040	
13:34:39	210	0.09		70	3											FL050	
13:35:45	110	0.09		20	3											FL060	
13:36:50	80	0.10		10	3											FL070	
13:37:50	85	0.10		20	3											FL080	
13:38:36	110	0.11		40	3											FL090	
13:39:38	120	0.10	150	50	2											FL100	
13:40:42	105	0.11		30	3											FL110	
13:41:55	75	0.10		20	2											FL120 PCASP Heater on	
13:42:53	85	0.09		15	1											FL130	
13:44:01	90	0.11		20	3											FL140	
13:45:00	100	0.11	151	20	2											FL150	
13:46:00	50	0.11		10	1											FL160	
13:47:20	20	0.08		2	1											FL170	
13:48:25	10	0.06		10												FL180	
13:49:28	8	0.07		1	1											FL190	

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B302	Date	28 Jun 2007	Operator	Doug Anderson	Page No.	1 of 1
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GMT	Sonde No.	Event <i>eg land, splashdown</i>	Comments <i>pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
11:27:09	1	Launch	526.60 -6.80 41.58 116.10 15.00 -14.60 -14.684400 17.928800
11:33:47	1	Land	1005.69 30.35 999.00 259.21 3.63 -12.11 -14.702927 17.927602

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B301

Date:

27 JUN 2007

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)	Bottom inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)
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Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run1	243-07	----	----	Bottom	11:14:00	11:43:00	R2.1/R3.1	1073	R2.1, 2.2 kfeet, sigma_scatt ~440 Mm-1, R3.1, 3 kfeet, sigma_scatt ~440 Mm-1
Filters run1	244-07	----	----	Top	11:14:00	11:43:00	R2.1/R3.1	1465	
Filters run 2	245-07	----	----	Bottom	11:45:40	12:15:00	R3.1	1040	R3.1, 3 kfeet, sigma_scatt ~440 Mm-1
Filters run 2	246-07	----	----	Top	11:45:40	12:15:00	R3.1	1505	
Filters run 3	247-07	----	----	Bottom	12:19:00	12:49:00	R3.1	1101	R3.1, 3 kfeet, sigma_scatt ~160 Mm-1
Filters run 3	248-07	----	----	Top	12:19:00	12:49:00	R3.1	1450	
Filters run 4	257-07	----	----	Bottom	12:52:40	13:32:21	R3.1	1400	R3.1, 3 kfeet, sigma_scatt ~110 Mm-1
Filters run 4	249-07	----	----	Top	12:52:40	13:32:21	R3.1	1976	
Filters run 5	258-07	----	----	Bottom	----	----	----	----	BLANK
Filters run 5	250-07	----	----	Top	----	----	----	----	BLANK

B301_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

08:33:49.28 --- - - - -
08:33:49.28 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
08:33:49.28 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                                tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
08:33:49.28 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B301
08:33:49.28 --- - - - -
08:34:02.97 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:34:05.75 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:34:08.81 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:34:23.87 SWS - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
08:34:26.99 SWS - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
08:34:40.83 USH - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
08:34:43.98 USH - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
08:34:46.98 LSH - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
08:34:50.58 LSH - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
08:34:53.28 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:34:53.28 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:34:53.29 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:35:08.59 USH - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
08:35:12.80 USH - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 150ms.
08:35:21.23 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:35:21.25 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:35:21.27 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:35:25.83 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:35:29.17 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:35:29.25 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:35:29.37 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:35:29.59 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:35:35.58 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:35:37.50 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:35:41.04 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:35:43.51 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:35:45.44 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:35:48.97 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:35:54.54 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:35:54.59 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:35:54.92 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:36:02.47 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:36:02.68 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:36:02.87 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:36:07.25 --- - - - - *** preflight tests OK
08:36:15.74 --- - - - - *** modules to idle
08:36:18.90 SWS - - - - Idling
08:36:20.86 USH - - - - Idling
08:36:22.21 LSH - - - - Idling
09:43:42.54 --- - - - - *** SWS tp 90AFT
09:45:56.61 --- - - - - *** taxiing
09:48:36.71 --- - - - - *** Flight B301 Niamey to Noaukchott
09:49:42.46 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:49:42.46 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:49:42.46 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:49:46.65 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:49:46.71 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:49:46.74 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:49:54.59 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:49:54.80 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:49:55.00 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:50:03.58 --- - - - - *** shutters inop reseetting
09:50:09.79 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:50:12.99 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:50:17.85 SWS - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 250ms.
09:50:20.65 SWS - - - 200 NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 200ms.
09:50:23.74 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
09:50:28.03 USH - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
09:50:32.87 SWS - - 75 - VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 75ms.
09:50:35.92 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:50:38.37 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.

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09:50:45.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:50:47.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:50:48.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:50:51.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:50:54.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:50:59.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:51:19.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** take off..start of P1
09:53:20.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:53:20.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:53:20.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:53:22.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:53:25.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:53:28.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:53:49.60	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
09:53:56.50	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 150ms.
09:54:00.30	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 350ms.
09:54:05.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:54:09.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:07:08.76	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
10:07:13.59	USH	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
10:07:17.97	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
10:07:20.44	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
10:07:22.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:22.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:22.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:25.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:07:26.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:07:30.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:10:13.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud
10:15:44.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** in run 1 at FL220 ...above dust
10:16:02.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** cirrus above
10:24:09.14	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
10:24:12.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:20.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:24:34.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud above and below
10:33:00.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 176Aft
10:46:53.24	LSH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
10:46:56.14	LSH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
10:46:59.74	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
10:47:02.43	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
10:47:04.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:04.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:04.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:06.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:08.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:10.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:00.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run 1 start profile 2
11:02:54.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** cirrus above almost gone
11:03:26.01	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 400ms.
11:03:30.41	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
11:03:33.44	LSH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
11:03:36.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:44.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:56.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 4000ft in dust layer
11:12:08.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws nadir view
11:13:35.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** bumpy
11:13:50.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** ground visible below
11:14:01.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** end P2 start R2.1
11:14:14.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 2200ft
11:17:07.85	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
11:17:11.28	LSH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
11:17:13.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:19.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:24.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** end r2.1 start p3
11:17:29.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:29.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:29.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:31.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:33.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

11:17:35.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:43.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:43.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:43.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:45.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:46.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:49.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:18:08.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** end P3 start R3.1 at 3000ft
11:21:38.86	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:21:45.30	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 10ms.
11:21:49.85	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 50ms.
11:21:54.02	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
11:21:56.91	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 25ms.
11:22:00.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:01.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:23:27.55	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 10ms.
11:23:30.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:23:32.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:08.12	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
11:26:14.17	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
11:26:19.17	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
11:26:21.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:24.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:13.95	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:27:18.32	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 10ms.
11:27:21.05	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
11:27:22.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:27:23.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:31:44.54	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
11:31:48.67	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 75ms.
11:31:52.54	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
11:31:54.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:56.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:48.95	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:32:51.85	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 10ms.
11:32:55.59	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
11:32:57.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:58.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:34:34.65	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
11:34:36.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:42.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:37:05.66	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
11:37:09.91	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 75ms.
11:37:14.47	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
11:37:15.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:37:18.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:37:57.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** first of 3 50A to 50F scanning runs coming up
11:38:24.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 50A
11:38:32.30	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
11:38:35.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:38.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:39:45.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** 50F
11:40:40.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** 40A
11:41:54.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** 40F
11:43:04.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** 30A
11:43:11.47	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
11:43:14.27	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 150ms.
11:43:16.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:18.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:28.19	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 25ms.
11:43:29.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:31.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:44:14.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** 30F
11:45:21.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** 20A
11:46:20.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** 20F
11:47:27.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10A
11:47:37.08	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 10ms.
11:47:40.27	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 50ms.

11:47:42.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:42.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:48:39.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10F
11:49:44.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** 0 degrees
11:49:51.73	SWS	-	-	-	25	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 25ms.
11:49:55.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:49:55.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:51:16.31	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:53:51.57	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
11:53:55.45	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 75ms.
11:53:58.79	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 25ms to 200ms.
11:54:00.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:02.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:02.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:03.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:06.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:08.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:55:03.88	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:55:09.86	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 10ms.
11:55:12.89	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
11:55:15.98	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
11:55:18.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:55:19.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:59:31.57	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
11:59:35.27	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 75ms.
11:59:38.52	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 200ms.
11:59:41.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:59:41.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:59:41.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:59:44.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:59:44.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:59:47.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:00:45.34	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:00:48.54	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 10ms.
12:00:51.74	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
12:00:53.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:55.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:05:22.39	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:05:35.48	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 75ms.
12:05:38.84	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
12:05:41.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:05:43.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:06:42.03	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:06:46.85	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 10ms.
12:06:49.37	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
12:06:59.71	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
12:07:02.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:07:03.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:09:01.96	SWS	-	-	-	25	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 25ms.
12:09:04.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:04.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:11:00.95	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:11:05.51	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 25ms to 200ms.
12:11:08.45	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 50ms.
12:11:11.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:11:11.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:11:11.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:11:14.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:11:15.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:11:17.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:12:04.90	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:12:08.55	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 10ms.
12:12:11.78	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
12:12:13.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:12:14.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:12:20.07	SWS	-	-	-	25	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 25ms.
12:12:21.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:12:22.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:16:50.54	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R

12:16:54.89	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 75ms.
12:16:58.35	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 25ms to 150ms.
12:17:00.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:02.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:11.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** thin cirrus above
12:20:28.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** nadir views for the moment
12:58:02.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:58:02.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:58:02.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:58:04.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:58:06.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:58:08.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:30.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:30.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:30.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:32.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:34.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:36.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:23:12.83	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:23:16.15	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 10ms.
13:23:18.33	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
13:23:20.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:22.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:24:37.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** little bits cirrus above
13:26:16.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** now motly clear above
13:27:42.66	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:28:04.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:07.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:28:08.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:14.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:28:14.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:15.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:15.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:16.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:28:18.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:28:20.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:28:30.04	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 75ms.
13:28:34.20	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
13:28:36.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:39.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:28:57.80	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:29:01.71	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 25ms.
13:29:04.53	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 10ms.
13:29:07.63	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
13:29:10.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:29:12.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:32:22.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** end R3.1 start profile 3
13:32:33.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** P4
13:38:20.98	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:38:24.22	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 75ms.
13:38:26.77	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
13:38:29.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:31.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:38:50.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 172Aft for profil climb
13:50:40.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** end P start R
13:50:56.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** at FL200
13:52:00.88	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:52:06.48	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
13:52:11.38	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
13:52:14.49	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
13:52:18.29	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
13:52:28.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:28.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:28.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:31.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:32.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:34.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:04:15.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run and start profile descent
14:04:20.12	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F

14:04:24.53	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 400ms.
14:04:28.43	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
14:04:31.04	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
14:04:55.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 3F for profile descent
14:10:35.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** just ino the dust
14:10:41.05	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
14:10:43.64	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
14:10:46.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:49.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:15:30.64	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
14:15:34.28	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 25ms.
14:15:37.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:15:37.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:15:37.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:15:39.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:15:40.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:15:43.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:39.98	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
14:24:42.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:43.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:31:30.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile and landing at Nouakchott
14:31:50.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 90A and data stop

ARIES flight log

Flight: B301

page 1 of 3

Date: 27/June/07

Operator(s): S. ROGERS

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: NIAMEY TO NOUAKHOUTT.

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
08 45 35	On the pan ↑ TAKEOFF	1x60	CH	C	71	41	Scrub 1 (1x60 CBB; 1x60 HBB)
10 14 42	FL230	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 15 59		480x1	N	C	71	42	Motty cloud ⁽²⁾ below, surface visible Some cloud above.
10 20 01		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 21 19		480x1	N	C	71	41	
10 25 22		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 26 39		480x1	N	C	71	41	
10 30 45		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 31 57		480x1	N	C	71	41	
10 35 59		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 37 16		480x1	N	C	71	41	
10 41 18		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 42 32		480x1	N	C	71	41	
10 46 34		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 47 52		480x1	N	C	71	41	
10 51 51		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 53 03		480x1	N	C	71	41	Aborted at end of run.
10 53 54	↓	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 13 47	MPA 2300 alt	1x60	CH	C	71	41	~ 1000 ft above terrain. 1245
10 15 03	MPA	360x1	N	C	71	41	Bumpy.
10 17 07	↑	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 18 22	3300 alt 7:33	360x1	N	C	71	41	
11 21 25		1x60	CH	C			
11 22 50		360x1	Z	O	70	41	Opens at shut
11 25 5-		120x1	N	C			
11 27 03		1x60	CH	C			
11 28 16		360x1	Z	O	71	42	
11 31 30		120x1	N	C	71	42	
11 32 39		1x60	CH	C			

ARIES flight log

Flight: B301

page 2 of 3

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
11 34 30 34		360x1	Z	O	71	42	
11 36 49		120x1	N	C	71	43	
11 37 52		1x60	CH	C	71	43	
11 39 18		360x1	Z	O	71	43	
11 42 30		120x1	N	C	71	43	
11 43 44		1x60	CH	C			
11 45 04		360x1	Z	O	71	43	As CBS is wandering up again (usual
11 48 22		1x60	CH	O	71	44	low level tropics problem) I'm leaving
11 49 59		360x1	Z	O	71	44	the shutter open all the time to see
11 53 16		180 x1	N	C			if that helps keep it cool.
11 54 57		1x60	CH	C	71	45	(*Note HBB shows affected too much)
11 56 20		360x1	Z	O	71	45	Opening at start of view.
11 59 30		120x1	N	C	71	45	
11 00 39		1x60	CH	C	71	45	
12 02 00		360x1	Z	O	71	45	
12 05 15		120x1	N	C	71	45	
12 06 22		360 x1	Z				← CH 1x60 'C'
12 07 40		360x1	Z	O	70	44	
12 10 54		120x1	N	C	71	45	
12 11 57		1x60	CH	C	71	45	
12 13 15		360x1	Z	O	70	45	Still low, still bumpy.
12 16 45		120x1	N	C	71	45	
12 17 55		1x60	CH	C	71	45	
12 19 13		480x1	N	C	71	45	
12 23 14		1x60	CH	C	71	44	
12 24 33		480x1	N	C	71	44	
12 28 35		1x60	CH	C	71	44	
12 29 58		480x1	N	C	71	44	Wadi below
12 33 54		1x60	CH	C	71	44	
12 35 18		480x1	N	C	71	44	
12 39 20		1x60	CH	C	71	44	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B301

page 3 of 3

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
12 40 38		480x1	N	C	71	43	13 30
12 44 39		1x60	CH	C	71	43	
12 46 04		480x1	N	C	71	43	
12 50 05		1x60	CH	C	71	43	
12 51 21		480x1	N	C	71	43	
12 55 25		1x60	CH	C	71	43	
12 56 54		1x60	CH	C	71	43	
12 58 09		480x1	N	C	71	43	
13 02 11		1x60	CH	C	71	43	
13 03 34		480x1	N	C	71	43	
13 07 35		1x60	CH	C	71	43	
13 08 54		480x1	N	C	71	43	Aborted: key fumble led to N+10°
13 09 36		360x1	N	C	71	43	
13 12 38		1x60	CH	C	71	43	
13 13 58		480x1	N	C	71	43	Still low, still bumpy.
13 18 00		1x60	CH	C	71	43	
13 19 19		480x1	N	C	71	43	
13 23 10		1x60	CH	C	71	43	
13 24 27		360x1	Z	O	70	43	
13 27		120x1	N	C	71	44	
13 28		1x60	CH	C	71	44	
13 29 57		240x1	Z	O	71	44	Opening during start of view
13 32			CH				Aborted - too soon after shutter close
13 33 42		1x60	CH	C	71	44	
13 50 34	FL	1x60	CH	C	71	42	
13 51 55		480x1	N	C	71	41	
13 55 57		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 57 14		480x1	N	C	71	41	
14 01 21		1x60	CH	C	71	41	

B301

Flight Manager

- ✓ WDW
- ✓ GIN
- ✓ CGPS
- ✓ INU
- ✓ DRS
- ✓ JW
- ✓ PSAP

- ✓ HEIMANN.

Flight:

B301

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevzorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

**Report Created 29/08/2007
08:43:43**

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

02/07/2007 13:31:23

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B301

Date: 27 June 2007

Instruments

1. dry neph relative humidity suspect
2. nevz U/S
3. GIN data incorrect until rebooted about 13:40
4. de iced true temp isn't correct (JimH), possibly relates to true/dewpoint anomaly previously reported
5. ins velocity north; oscillations with 3 min period – example 1120 > 1150 (John Marsham)

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

New plot, same times

Flight B301 13:49:00

Heading 268 deg Speed 273 knots Height 18.6kft Press 492mb

Lat 17°48.0'N Long 12°54.0'W Wind 6 ms-1/ 83 deg

Temp -5.85C Dewpoint -36.49C

From 11:17 to 13:32

Current values			
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	49737	secs	☒ All
++++ NEPH BLUE SP	1.37	m-1	☐
++++ NEPH GREEN SP	0.1	m-1	☐
++++ NEPH RED SP	-0.24	m-1	☐

B301 Images Emailed In Flight

EEA041 MSG dust RGB 27 Jun 2007 0830 UTC

EEA041_20070627_0830.jpg

EEA041 MSG dust RGB 27 Jun 2007 1015 UTC

EEA041_20070627_1015.jpg

EEO41 MSG dat RGB 27 Jun 2007 1230 UTC

EEO41_20070627_1230.jpg

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B301:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Wet Nephelometer	No operator on GERBIL

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	05 Sep 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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